

Guideline: "Sustainify" your syllabi

This guideline is intended to provide a checklist of questions that can help a program coordinator or an individual instructor to integrate sustainability into their educational components. It was developed at the IT faculty and may have to be adapted for other disciplines.

Labeling Definition

To be **either related or focused** the course must:

1. Engage the important challenges of achieving sustainability, and ways to overcome them (explicitly or implicitly)
2. Cover the social, economic and environmental dimensions of sustainability

To be sustainability **related** the course must:

1. Cover two or more sustainability criteria through one distinct graded/evaluated course component or module, including an assignment, test, set of readings or discussion
2. Concentrate on one of the listed sustainability criterion as the central part of a course topic that comprises at least **25 percent** of course's evaluated material

To be sustainability **focused** the course must:

1. Have a theme (covered by at least **95 percent** of course material) that concentrates on at least one of the listed sustainability criteria
2. Spend half of the course concentrated (through tests and assignments, discussions and/or readings) on two or more of the listed sustainability criteria
3. Have a theme that examines an issue or topic using at least one of the sustainability criteria as a lens

Guidance questions

1. How can my course relate to sustainability and how to detail that?
→ Type of course and overall topic of the course
 - a. Which SDGs or sustainability criteria (page 2) can the overall topic be related to?
 - i. Theory course: sustainability examples
 - ii. Applied XYZ -> get a sustainability-interested 'client' (or surrogate-client)
 - b. Do I want the course to be sustainability-related (~25%) or focused (~95%)?
2. How can the syllabus **reflect** this?

- a. **Learning objectives** (if not in there, it ain't happening): refer to specific SDG(s)
 - b. Name objective, how implemented in teaching, and how assessed (constructive alignment - at least exemplarily so instructor still has freedom)
3. Which **sustainability competencies** can be taught within your course?
There are two frameworks to choose from:
- a. The [EU GreenComp](#) framework with 12 competencies
 - b. Or the subset of 5 sustainability competencies by [[Wiek & al.](#), [Brundiens et al. 2021](#)]
4. Individual **topics** to cover within the course
- a. What aspects of the course topic are most related to sustainability?
 - i. E.g., software analysis and design: environmental impact, user accessibility
 - ii. E.g., cybersecurity fundamentals: company assets, social engineering
 - b. Find an SDG to relate: 1 no poverty, 2 zero hunger, 3 good health, 4 quality education, 5 gender equality, 6 clean water, 7 clean energy, 8 decent work, 9 infrastructure, 10 reduce inequality, 11 sustainable communities, 12 responsible consumption, 13 climate action, 14 life below water, 15 life on land, 16 peace, 17 partnerships
 - c. Find the sustainability dimension to relate it to (environmental, economic, social, individual, technical)
5. Teaching **methods**?
- a. Guest lectures: invite someone if you don't feel expert enough
 - b. Client with sustainability concern: for individual assignments or team project
 - c. Module that has a case on a sustainability system, e.g. water system, waste sorting, ...
 - d. Student activity for them to come up with a sustainability-related example
 - e. Reference list of helpful papers for inspiration [[Sprei et al.](#), [Gupta et al.](#), [Sam Mann](#), [Rockström](#), [Daniel Pargman & Elina Eriksson](#), [Lorenz Hilty](#), [Steve Easterbrook](#), [Håkan Burden](#)]
6. Evaluation?
- a. How show that sustainability was considered and students now know more about it?
 - b. How can students integrate this in their 'portfolio'? (e.g., for resume, CV, website, showcase collection, etc.)
7. Involve students
- a. Find some current students in your course and discuss it with them. Some are well informed about sustainability and happy to contribute.
 - b. Offer early ideas and discuss them and ask if that was helpful.

Resources

- "Sustainify" Worksheet: DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15349671
 - Sustainable Development Goals <https://sdgs.un.org>
 - GreenComp framework: <https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC128040>
 - Association for the Advancement of Sustainability in Higher Education <https://www.aashe.org> and their Sustainability Tracking, Assessment and Rating System STARS <https://stars.aashe.org>
 - Sustainability Competencies Framework [[Wiek et al. 2011](#); [Redman & Wiek 2021](#); [Brundiens et al. 2021](#)]
 - GU Guideline on sustainability labeling of courses study programmes (2014) https://www.medarbetarportalen.gu.se/digitalAssets/1575/1575956_slutv.eng-hum--rkning-p---engelska-dokument-160523-br.pdf
The following criteria should be considered according to the objectives and content of each field of education.
1. **Sustainability as a concept:** The history in a global context of the concept of sustainability and sustainable development and the current study field related to global challenges.

2. **Analysis from a globalisation perspective:** How products, services, or activities in their own lives or in the future professional profession affect the natural environment, social conditions and the economy in a global perspective, both today and in the future.
3. **Natural limits:** Demographic trends and lifestyle in relation to the exploitation of natural resources, or the finite capacity of natural ecosystems to provide for human needs.
4. **Maintaining ecosystems:** Conservation of natural resources and practices to protect and maintain the integrity of viable ecosystems in the face of rising human demands.
5. **Human rights and social equity:** Distribution, discrimination, health and poverty issues and the mutual interaction between social inequality, poor health, the natural environment and people's opportunities for good living conditions.
6. **Values, culture and ethics:** How norms, culture, religion, ethics and social conditions can shape human behaviour toward the natural world.
7. **Consumer and customer power:** How demands for environmental consideration and social responsibility from private and public clients and consumers affects individuals, policies and corporate strategies and business opportunities.
8. **Governance and management:** How regulations, policies, economic policy instruments and voluntary agreements, and leadership shape human behaviour and the actions of nations and companies in respect of the natural world and social issues.
9. **Planning and design:** How community planning and product and service design can influence human well-being and human impact on the natural environment.
10. **Actors' work and responsibility:** The efforts of various global and local actors, and their monitoring of environmental performance and social and economic responsibility.